

Az egészségmegőrzést támogató péksütemény termékek fejlesztés során felhasznált gyümölcs-alapanyagok és töltelékváltozatok vizsgálata

Analysis of Fruit-Based Ingredients and Filling Variants Used in the Development of Bakery Products Supporting Health Preservation

The project was implemented within the framework of the following project: GINOP-2.1.2-8-1-4-16-2017-00299

Methods:

Analysis of Element Composition in Foods

Sample Preparation: After a 30-minute thawing period at room temperature, all frozen samples were processed into finished products by baking at 220°C for 10 minutes (n=9). A dry homogeneous sample was prepared from the finished product according to MSZ 20501-1:2007; Section 1. The combined samples underwent elemental analytical preparation using microwave digestion according to MSZ EN 13805:2002.
Measurement Method: EPA Method 6010C:2007 (ICP-OES)

Analysis of Fiber Content in Foods

Sample Preparation: After a 30-minute thawing period at room temperature, all frozen samples were processed into finished products by baking at 220°C for 10 minutes (n=9). A dry homogeneous sample was prepared from the finished product according to MSZ 20501-1:2007; Section 1.
Measurement Method: MSZ 20501-1:2007; Section 2

Analysis of Protein Content in Foods

Sample Preparation: After a 30-minute thawing period at room temperature, all frozen samples were processed into finished products by baking at 220°C for 10 minutes (n=9). The analytical sample was prepared from the finished product according to MSZ 20501-1:2007; Section 1.
Measurement Method: MSZ 20501-1:2007; Section 7

Analysis of Fat Content in Foods

Sample Preparation: After a 30-minute thawing period at room temperature, all frozen samples were processed into finished products by baking at 220°C for 10 minutes (n=9). The analytical sample was prepared from the finished product according to MSZ 20501-1:2007; Section 1.
Measurement Method: MSZ 20501-1:2007; Section 4

Analysis of Total Polyphenol Content in Foods

Sample Preparation: After a 30-minute thawing period at room temperature, all frozen samples were processed into finished products by baking at 220°C for 15 minutes (n=9). The separated fillings from the finished product were combined and homogenized.
Measurement Method: Singleton VL, Rossi JA (1965) Colorimetry of Total Phenolics with Phosphomolybdic-Phosphotungstic Acid Reagents. Am J Enol Vitic 16:144–158.

Results:

No.	Sample Name	Total Polyphenol Content (GE/100g)	Total/Unsaturated Fatty Acid Ratio	Mg Content (mg/kg)	Crude Protein Content (g/kg)	Crude Fiber Content (g/kg)
1	Black blueberry	707	1460 mg polyunsaturated/kg	3	10	24
2	Black blackberry	880	2000 mg polyunsaturated/kg	60	14	63
3	Black chokeberry	720	1200 mg polyunsaturated/kg	55	14	53
4	Raspberry	650	3700 mg polyunsaturated/kg	220	12	65
5	Strawberry	590	1202 mg polyunsaturated/kg	170	6	54
6	Acai (processed)	920	<100 mg	<1	nd.	10
7	Red Berry Mix (processed) "A"	897	3200/1250	149	20	46
8	Red Berry Mix (processed) "B"	863	2800/1400	142	13	58
9	Red Berry Mix (processed) "C"	819	4500/2800	57	20	49
10	Red Berry Mix (processed) "D"	833	3200/1750	134	14	54
11	Red Berry Mix (processed) "E"	813	3500/1245	132	17	59
12	Red Berry Mix (processed) "F"	847	3800/1500	93	10	43
13	Apple Filling "A"	600	1000/410	44	3	14
14	Apple Filling "B"	687	900/450	45	2	12
15	Apple Filling "C"	797	950/500	46	3	16
16	Apple Filling "D"	617	990/410	44	2	12
17	Tomato (processed) "A"	744	2000/800	110	90	12
18	Tomato (processed) "B"	735	1980/800	120	89	15
19	Tomato (processed) "C"	686	2020/750	112	73	16
20	Tomato (processed) "D"	697	1900/790	115	55	19
21	Tomato (processed) "E"	643	1925/820	120	49	12
22	Pea (processed) "A"	25	1	nd.	802	nd.
23	Pea (processed) "B"	29	2	nd.	795	nd.
24	Pea (processed) "C"	32	3	nd.	816	nd.
25	Pea (processed) "D"	30	6	nd.	825	1